

Supplement of

How does the lifetime of detrained cirrus impact the high-cloud radiative effect in the tropics?

George Horner and Edward Gryspeerdt

Correspondence to: George Horner (g.horner20@imperial.ac.uk)

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Figure S1: Histogram of lifetimes of detrained cirrus using a 20% threshold, and a 10% threshold for the lifetime cutoff point.

Figure S2: Change in the lifetime extension CRE using the two different calculated cutoffs from S1.

Figure S3: As in Figure 7, but controlling for albedo by only showing CRE of trajectories that exist over ocean, for both land-origin and ocean-origin trajectories.